

Influence of Users Education on Students Use of Library Resources in Federal Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigated the influence of user education on students' use of library resources in federal polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The research was guided by three research questions aligned with its objectives, focusing on the extent of library resource use, the influence of user education, and its significance.

Method: A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study population consisted of 1,000 HND students registered with polytechnic libraries in North-East, Nigeria, with a sample size of 500 HND students selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and means, with a criterion mean benchmark of 2.50.

Findings/Results: The findings indicated a high extent of library resource use among students ($M > 2.50$). User education had a positive influence on the use of library resources, with a statistically significant impact on students' utilization of library information resources. Notably, students utilized printed resources more frequently than electronic resources.

Implications: The results suggest that user education significantly enhances students' ability to effectively utilize library resources, particularly printed materials, in federal polytechnics. This underscores the importance of structured educational programs to improve resource access and usage.

Conclusion: The study concludes that user education significantly guides students in utilizing library information resources in federal polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria, with a notable preference for printed over electronic resources.

Recommendations: The study recommends that the management of federal polytechnic libraries in North-East, Nigeria, introduce additional user education programs and prioritize existing ones to further enhance students' effective use of library resources.

Keywords: Federal Polytechnics, Use of Library Resources, User Education, North-East, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Use of library information resources involves utilizing various materials by patrons available in the libraries to support research, education, and personal enrichment. These library resources include books, electronic database, journals and multimedia materials. Users can access these resources to find information, conduct research, enhance their knowledge and complete academic or personnel projects. Library information resources are typically organized by librarians and made available to help users locate the information they need. By effectively using library information resources individual can broaden their horizons, stay informed and engage in lifelong learning. Innocent (2022) stated that the use of library and information resources is very important as to the research output of researchers in universities, because it is perceived that the use of these resources may contribute to the research output and the development of the nation at large. Consequently, Mwalukasa (2022) asserted that the use of information resources in libraries help to fulfill the objectives of establishing the university and these enables the university library supports to accomplishment of the main objective of higher learning institution in provision of high quality education.

User education is crucial to empower individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively navigate library resources and information sources. User education programme aim to teach library users how to search for information, evaluate sources and utilize various library services to meet their information needs. User education promotes effective library usage among students. Negi et al. (2023) defined user education as various programmes of instruction, education and exploration provided by libraries to users to enable them to make effective, efficient and independent use of information resources and services to which these libraries provide access. There is every tendency that the capacity of a library user to exploit information resources in any institution library such as

polytechnic library would depend on the level of his/her user education programmes received to efficiently and effectively use the information resources. Thus, it is against this backdrop that the researchers intends to investigate users' education on students' use of library information resources in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The use of the library information resources is crucial for continue existences of the library. It helps in the conduct of research, gaining of knowledge and accessing of a wide range of learning materials. Libraries provide a vast collection of books, journals, magazines, newspapers, and other resources that can support individuals in their academic studies, professional development, or personal interest. The regular or frequency use of the library resources would help users improve their reading and comprehension skills. Preliminary investigation shown that polytechnic libraries in North-east, Nigeria are always full to their capacity during examination periods but experience low patronage when the examinations are over.

Extant literature has shown that majority of students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria does not make good use of library information resources as evident by Issa et al. (2024). Mashaba and Pretorius (2023) equally reported that students in Nigerian tertiary institutions under use the library information resources (both print and electronic) as this could result to poor academic performance. Poor academic performance is as a result of poor knowledge acquisition which intentionally leads to not meeting society's requirement for employment, poor standard of living, non-measuring up in the society and bad behaviour such as stealing, lack of user education programmes and inadequate possession of ICT skills by students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. To address this research concern, the researcher investigated user education on students' use of library resources in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives were to:

1. determine the extent of use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria;
2. examine the influence of user education on the use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria;
3. determine the significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Governor and Mesagan (2024) conducted a study to investigate the user education practice for effective use of library resources in College of Education in Delta States, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study was guided by five (5) research question inline with the research objectives. A stratified random sampling technique was use to select a sample size of 252 registered library users. Questionnaire was the research instrument used for data collection. Data was analyzed using frequency distribution and percentages run on SPSS. The findings revealed that the influence of time allocation for the programme was in the students' inability to attend the programme because it was conducted while they were yet to settle down for studies, the time allocated is not enough, it does not permit practical's. Inadequate numbers of staff to handle the programme, lack of follow up instructions, inadequate ICT facilities for the programme were identified as challenges. The study concluded that the use of the library mainly depends on the different features that make up the library, user education programs such as orientation, use of library lessons and guided tour allow the library to sanitize learner and generate appropriate understanding of the library. The study recommended that government should endeavor to formulate a policy that would make user education programme becomes a most to be taken by all new students, and also user education should be broken into two semesters to facilitate practical's.

Umoriya (2023) conducted a study to investigate the impact of user education on use of library resources by undergraduate students of university of Abuja, Nigria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study was guided by four (4) research questions in line with the research objectives. Krejcie and Morgan (1070) Table was used to select a sample size of 379 undergraduate students of the university. A structured questionnaire was use as instrument for data collection. Data were analyse using frequency counts, percentage and mean. Findings revealed that user education has positive impact on the undergraduate students' use of library resources and their academic performance as it greatly improves their ability to find needed information and use the catalogue effectively to retrieve information and makes them to be aware of the scope of the library among others. The study concluded that user education programmes significantly impact on use of library resources by undergraduate students. The study recommended that, there should be provision for adequate and proper ventilation within the libraries studied.

Adeolu (2022) conducted a study to investigate the usage and library resources among engineering undergraduate students of private universities in Oyo state, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study was guided by seven (7) research questions inline with the research objectives. Simple random sampling was use to select a sample size of 140 undergraduate engineering students. Questionnaire was used to collect data. Data collected was analyses using frequency count, percentage, and mean score. The findings revealed that, lecture method was the most 132(97.8%) approach of delivering user education. Seventy-six of the respondents indicated that, user education acquainted them with information sources and services. Findings equally revealed that, textbooks were the most 71(52.6%) very readily available information materials while

50(37.0%) respondents indicated that, literature search assistance was the most available information service also revealed that, 99(50.78%) respondents used library resources daily, 49(25.12%) respondents used library materials once a week, while 47(24.10%) used library resources once a month. The study concluded that utilization of information resources and services is a function of effective methods of user education among engineering undergraduates students in private universities in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study recommended that the most applicable and effective methods of user education should be used such as use of library course, lecture and library orientation.

Ejiro (2021) conducted a study to investigate the influence of library environment and user education on undergraduates' use of library at the College of Education Warri, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The study was guided by five (5) research questions inline with the research objectives. Random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 400 undergraduate students of the College. The study used questionnaire as the instrument for data collection, while the data collected were analyzed using frequency distribution and percentages. The findings revealed that the customer education methods were library orientation for fresh learners and use of library course with guided library tour; the students use the library in order to study and read for exams, most undergraduates used the library daily or weekly. Insufficient technological equipment to be used for electronic sources and bad network / internet connectivity to access electronic databases were some of the main problems of using the college library. The study concluded that user education in academic library services is very important because it determines the extent to which the library resources and services would be sponsored and used by students. The study recommended that students should always create time to attend user education programmes organized by the university libraries, either as orientation or special training sessions on new services.

Okonoko and Eruvwe (2020) conducted a study to investigate the influence of user education on library usage among students of college of education in South-South, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Four (4) research questions were formulated which are in line with the objectives to guides the study. Random sample method was use to sample 373 library users of the colleges under study. A questionnaire was use as the instrument for data collection. Data was analyzed using statistical mean. The findings revealed that there are user education programmes in College of Education libraries in South-South, Nigeria. Such as guided tour and lecture user education has positive influence on library usage among students of college of education in South-South, Nigeria and it improves their ability to find needed information effectively. The study concluded that user education user has positive influence on library usage among students of college of education. The study recommended that adequate user education infrastructure should be provided in college of education libraries in South-South, Nigeria to facilitate student's participation in the user education programmers.

Ayanfemi and innocent (2020) conducted a study to investigate the influence of user education on the use of library resources in federal polytechnic, Idah, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design for the study. The study was guided by (4) research questions inline with the research objectives. Three hundred students (300) were randomly sampled out of 600 library users. A questionnaire was used as an instrument of data collection. Data collected were analyzed using sample percentage and chi-square. The findings revealed a significant relationship between user education and use of library resources as it show that user education has a positive influence on library resources utilization. The study recommended that among the contemporary challenges associated with information explosion, that the course use of library be made two (2) credit units per semester and taken in both the two (2) semester for effective information literacy among students, and that user education programmes should be made mandatory for all fresh students.

Joseph (2020) conducted a study to investigate the degree to which students utilise the information resources in Rufus Giwa Polytechnic Library Owo, Ondo state, Nigeria. A descriptive design survey was used for the study. The method used was purposive sampling as 1,050 students were selected from the population of 6,550 students. Data were gathered using a questionnaire and its analysis involved the use of chi-square and basic percentages. The findings revealed that 97.14% response rate. Findings revealed that over fifty percent of the students reported using the library on a regular basis. 83.91% uses it to consult library books, 83.83% use it for various purposes, and the majority of users (84.02%) use it for social media. The study concluded that user education and library resource utilization significantly correlated, that is to say, user education influences library resource consumption in a favorable way. In order to address the current issues brought about by the information explosion, the study recommended that user education be enhanced and that the course "Use of Library" be offered for two credit units each semester.

Oyewo (2020) conducted a study to investigate the use of library information resources by undergraduate students in polytechnic library Ibadan, Nigeria. Cross-sectional survey style was adopted for this study. The study was guided by 8 research questions inline with the research objectives. Using a sampling fraction of 10% which is 438 of the population of each faculty in the South Campus of the Polytechnic Ibadan. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages. The findings revealed that (76.9%) of the respondents indicated that library instruction was very important and aided their studies, it is evident from the study that majority of the students who received training through library instruction programme became familiar with information resources and services and used them to their benefits. The study Concluded that library information literacy programme and library usage affect the use of library by the students both positively and negatively. The positive aspect is that it promotes the use of library and improves their academic performance while the negative aspect was that the students prefer the use of Internet than visiting the library.

The study recommended that the library should then intensify its orientation programmes since the Internet does not offer everything and library should be generally upgraded.

METHOD

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Population and sample as well as the use of data collection instrument used the descriptive survey research design because it is a survey type of research that is characterized. The study population comprised one thousand (1,000) Higher National Diploma (HND) students that registered with libraries in federal polytechnics in Northeast as at 2024/2025 academic session. The sample size was 500 registered HND students with polytechnic libraries and was determined using 50% sample fraction. Mole (2019) asserted that for population that run in several hundreds, i.e. between 900 – 1900, 41% to 60% sample fraction should be drawn. A close-ended structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. Data were analysed using frequency counts, percentage and mean with criterion mean of 2.50 benchmark. Weighted mean scores above or equal to the criterion mean are considered high extent or positive influence while weighted mean scores below the criterion mean are considered low extent or negative influence.

The null hypothesis was tested using ANOVA Model of regression analysis tested at 0.05 level of significance. The draft copies of questionnaire were validated by four lecturers in the Department of Library Information Science and two experts from Department of Test and Measurement all from Federal University of Technology, Minna for correctness and appropriateness of the language used, whether it is suitable and appropriate to answer the research questions of the study. The researchers administered 30 copies of the questionnaire to HND students in federal polytechnic, Bida and federal polytechnic, Kaduna for pilot testing using test re-test method. The overall reliability coefficient was 0.88 indicating that the instrument is reliable and excellent. A total of 500 copies of questionnaire were administered to HND students and 482 copies of questionnaire were retrieved representing 96.4% response rate.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the extent of use of library information resource by students of the federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria?

Table 1: Extent of use of library information resource by students of the federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria

S/N	Statement (n=482)	VHE 4		HE 3		LE 2		VLE 1		\bar{X}
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1	I use the textbooks in my institutional library for assignment.	267	55.4	188	39.0	27	5.6	0	0	3.49
2	I use the electronic books in my library for seminars.	160	33.2	157	32.6	32	6.6	133	27.6	2.71
3	I consult Journals for latest information and get new updates on a subject of study	230	47.7	168	34.9	77	16.0	7	1.5	3.28
4	I use electronic journals as they carry first-hands information of new ideas or discoveries.	137	28.4	157	32.6	1	0.2	187	38.8	2.58
5	I chlick the newspapers in my library for daily news headlines.	246	51.0	184	38.2	45	9.3	7	1.5	3.39
6	I browse through the electronic newspapers always for news update.	60	12.4	149	30.9	65	13.4	208	42.8	2.13
7	I consult reference materials. (Such as Dictionaries, Yearbooks, Gazetteers, and Encyclopaedias.) For meaning of words, fact about past events, information or data about discussion.	297	61.6	158	32.8	27	5.6	0	0	3.56
8	I use electronic database in my library to search for a particular document.	199	41.3	209	43.4	62	12.9	12	2.5	3.23
	Weighted Mean									3.05

Decision Mean: Average Weighted Mean = 3.05

Table 1 presented the extent of use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. The result showed that the respondents indicated that the following library information resources were highly used: reference materials with mean score of (3.56), textbooks with mean score of (3.49), newspapers with mean score of (3.39), hard copy journals with mean score of (3.28) and electronic databases with mean score of (3.23). However, electronic books with mean score (2.71), electronic journals with mean score of (2.58), and electronic newspapers with mean score of (2.13) recorded low extent of usage. Generally, the extent of use of library information resource by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria was high with the average weighted mean of 3.05 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50 benchmark.

Research Question Two: How does users education influence the use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria?

Table 2: User education influence on the use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria

S/N	STATEMENTS	VHE 4		HE 3		LE 2		VLE 1		\bar{X}
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1	User instruction enables me to know the units and sections in the polytechnic library	304	63.1	162	33.6	16	3.3	0	0	3.59
2	User instruction enables me to locate and retrieve materials from the shelves in the polytechnic library	267	55.4	209	43.4	6	1.2	0	0	3.54
3	User instruction enables me to navigate and evaluate information resources in the polytechnic library effectively.	337	69.9	131	27.2	10	2.1	4	0.8	3.66
4	Library orientation guides me on how to borrow books for home use	5	1.9	219	45.4	12	2.5	246	51.0	1.96
5	Library orientation educates me on the type of services rendered in the polytechnic library.	389	80.7	93	19.3	0	0	0	0	3.80
6	Library orientation guides me on how to locate and retrieve materials from the shelves in the library.	400	83.0	81	16.8	1	0.2	0	0	3.82
7	Guided tour educates me on the rules and regulation of the library.	310	64.3	153	31.7	13	2.7	6	1.2	3.59
8	Guided tour educates me on how to seek for assistance from the library staff.	269	55.8	192	39.8	19	3.9	1	0.4	3.51
9	Guided tour educates me on types of information resources available in the various units of the library.	283	58.7	178	36.9	17	3.5	4	0.8	3.53
10	Lecture on the use of library educates me on the opening hours of the library.	326	67.6	152	31.5	4	0.8	0	0	3.66
11	Lecture on the use of library educates me on how to search and retrieve materials.	351	72.8	131	27.2	0	0	0	0	3.72
12	Lecture on the use of library educates me on the types of materials allowed to be borrowed and not to be borrowed.	370	76.8	112	23.2	0	0	0	0	3.76
13	Bibliographic instruction enables me to use card catalogue to locate materials from the shelves.	124	25.7	34	7.1	296	61.4	28	5.8	2.53
14	Bibliographic instruction enables me to use Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC).	129	26.8	19	3.9	327	67.8	7	1.5	2.56
15	Bibliographic instruction such as: workshops and seminars, individual consultations, library guides, and tutoring educates me on how to locate books on the shelves using classification numbers	178	36.9	0	0	1	0.2	302	62.9	2.11
Weighted Mean										3.29

Decision Mean: Average Weighted Mean= 3.29

Table 2 showed the influence of users’ education on the use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. The result showed that the respondents perceived that eleven (11) out of fifteen (15) statements listed on user education had positive influence on the use of library information resources as the mean scores were above or equal to the average weighted mean of 3.29. On the other hand, the respondents perceived that the remaining four (4) statements had negative influence on the use of library information resources. Generally, the influence of users’ education on the use of library information resources by students in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria was positive with the average weighted mean of 3.29 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50 benchmark.

Research Question Three: What is the significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria

Table 3: ANOVA Model of Regression Analysis of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	104.091	2	104.091	796.118	0.00
Residual	62.759	480	0.131		
Total	166.850	482			

Dependent Variable: use of library information resources

Independent Variable(predictors) Constant: user education programme.

Table 3 showed Regression Sum of Squares = 104.091 which quantifies the variation in the dependent variable that the model explains. Residual = 62.759 quantifies the unexplained variation or error in the model. Total Sum of Squares = 166.850 quantifies the total variation in the dependent variable. Regression Mean Square = 104.091 explains the average amount of variation explained by the regression model. The F-statistic = 796.118 shows the regression model explains a high significant portion of the variation in the dependent variable. This p-value = 0.000 indicates the overall regression model is statistically significant since (0.000 < 0.05). Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria is rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Research objective one sought to find out the extent of use of the library information resources by students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. Findings revealed that there is a high extent of use of the library information resources by students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. This implies that students fully utilised the library information resources available in federal polytechnic libraries in North-east, Nigeria. This finding is in line with the findings of American Library Association (2020) that library information resources are acquired, organized and made accessible and by users to support their research, study, and information needs. This finding corroborate with finding of Innocent (2022) that use of library and information resources is very important as to the research output of researchers in Nigerian universities, because it is perceived that the use of these resources may contribute to the research output and the development of the nation at large. Similarly, Mwahukasa (2022) reported that most of the respondents mainly used special collection, general collection and special reserve at Sokoine University of Agriculture, Tanzania. Joseph et al. (2020) reported that over 50 % of the students use the library to consults resources on a regular basis at Rufus Giwa Polytechnic Library, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research objective two sought to find out the influence of user education on the use of library information resources by students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. Findings revealed that the influence of user education on the use of library information resources by students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria was positive. This implies that user education has significantly helped to guide the students on the use of library information resources in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. This is in line with the study of Ayanfemi and innocent (2020) who reported that there is a significant relationship between user education and use of library information resources. Similarly, Umoriya (2023) reported that user education has a positive impact on the undergraduate students' use of library resources and their academic performance as it greatly improves their ability to find needed information and use the catalogue effectively to retrieve information and makes them to be aware of the scope of the library among others.

Research objective three sought to find out the significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. The result for the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant influence of user education programmes on the use of library information resources by the students of federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. This finding corroborates the findings of Ayanfemi and innocent (2020) that there is a significant relationship between user education and use of library information resources. Similarly, Umoriya (2023) reported that user education has a positive impact on the undergraduate students' use of library resources and their academic performance as it greatly improves their ability to find needed information and use the catalogue effectively to retrieve information and makes them to be aware of the scope of the library among others.

CONCLUSION

The extent of use of library information resources was found to be high, the study also revealed a positive influence of users' education on the use of library information resources. Furthermore, there was a statistical significant influence of users' education programmes on the use of library and information resources in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. Thus, the study concluded that majority of the respondents predominantly utilised printed information resources than the electronic resources in federal polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria should leverage on the user education programmes available to put in place services that would facilitate the use of information resources in the library.
2. The management of Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria should introduce more user education programmes and prioritise the ones available.
3. The management of Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria should introduce the practical aspect of user education programmes to enhance what is being taught theoretically as it would help to enhance the search and evaluation of information seek by the students.

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